

A Preliminary Note on the Catalytic Oxidation of Paraffins.

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Air was passed through paraffin (m. p. 49° , iodine value 1.5 and of approximate composition $C_{24}H_{50}$) kept just below the boiling point and the mixed vapour was conducted over nickel prepared by reducing nickel oxide by means of hydrogen at 200° ; the rate of air was 0.01 cubic feet per minute. The issuing vapour was condensed in several successive receivers and the liquid thus obtained, was slightly acidic and gave all the tests of aldehydes. This was freed from the unchanged paraffin, by means of methyl alcohol, in which paraffin is not soluble. The methyl alcohol was evaporated away and the remaining liquid was treated with sodium bisulphite. Aldehyde was then set free from the bisulphite compound, taken up with ether, the ethereal solution dried and the ether evaporated off. The residue was then fractionally distilled at 15–17 mm. The following fractions were obtained:

		Temperature.	Yield per 100 g. of paraffin used.
I.	Up to	70°	1.25 g.
II.	„	$70^{\circ}-105^{\circ}$	3.30
III.	„	$105^{\circ}-115^{\circ}$	3.30
IV.	„	$115^{\circ}-130^{\circ}$	6.60
V.	„	$130^{\circ}-150^{\circ}$	5.30

Boiling points of the saturated aldehydes C_8 -, C_9 -, C_{10} - and C_{11} - are respectively 72° (20 mm.), 81° (14 mm.), 91° (11 mm), and 116° (18 mm.).

It thus appears that the liquid obtained by the oxidation of paraffins ($C_{24}H_{50}$) under the conditions of the experiment consists of the higher aldehydes. The total conversion of the paraffins into aldehydes was about 20%. Further investigations are in progress.

